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A STUDY ON GOVERNMENT REGULATED FOOD SAFETY TRAINING & CERTIFICATION (FoSTaC) PROGRAM FOR FOOD HANDLERS IN INDIA USING A HYBRID METHOD RESEARCH

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Abstract: Government is responsible to frame food laws for the country based on the latest scientific findings for creating safe food environment for public. These food laws are provided as guidelines to keep the food safe in food industry. Food safety training is needed to facilitate the knowledge of food laws to food handlers. In India, this training in the organized format is provided by Food Safety Training and Certification (FoSTaC) department of Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI), Government of India. Successful participants get the certificate in their name from the department designating them as Food Safety Supervisor (FSS). This paper explores the impact of FoSTaC training on food handlers working in catering sector of Indian food industry. Quantitative data analysis was done through hypotheses testing and qualitative through expert interviews & focus group discussions. This study found significant gap in the food safety knowledge of food handlers before the training. We conclude that the gap is fulfilled through this training program which is positive & statistically significant. Refresher training is important and policy change of compulsion of training to each Food Handler (FH) is urgent to enlarge the scope and impact of this training. More involvement of trainers and empanelled training partners are required for achieving the objectives of organized training under food safety training and certification program.

Keywords: FoSTaC, Food Safety Training, Food Handlers, Catering, Food Industry.

Introduction: One of the physiological need for living being is Food. Food is required for various functions in the body like energy, repair, development of organs, recovery from injury, immunity from diseases etc. Therefore, safe food is the first step for all human beings to remain healthy. To keep the food safe, science experiments have derived the parameters which should be used by food industry to keep the food safe and hygienic for human consumption. To ensure this, government make the food laws providing parameters and guidelines for use by the food handlers. Food law contains a guideline to provide food safety training to food handlers and food business operators.

In developed countries, food safety training is a mandatory requirement for food handler before joining the food industry. Depending on each country's law, food safety refresher training

is to be done once in each year, two year, 3 year, 4 year or as per change in the food law. This food safety training is of 2 levels – Basic and Advanced. Basic training is compulsory for all food handlers at any level of joining the industry. Advanced training is for senior level food handlers like managers, restaurant managers, sous chef and above designations in the company.

Indian Food Safety Ecosystem: In India, Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) is a statutory body under Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (FSSA, 2006). FSSAI is administered by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India for the implementation of food safety laws in India. It has been created for laying down science based standards for articles of food and to regulate their manufacture, storage, distribution, sale and import to ensure availability of safe and wholesome food

for human consumption.

In 2016, FSSAI created a department called as Food Safety Training & Certification (FoSTaC) to fulfil the provision of training to people involved in food sector. A team of experts from food sector are involved to create manual for food safety training in different sectors of food industry. Through FoSTaC certification food handlers are trained and certified as “Food Safety Supervisor” (FSS). Due to non-availability of experts within government for this training, FSSAI formulated a policy to provide these training through “Empanelled Training Partners”, who will do the work of organizing the food safety trainings under FSSAI banner. “Training of Trainers” (ToT) programs are run to create a pool of trainers & assessors, who will impart the training to food handlers across the country. As per policy requirement, minimum 01 out of 25 food handlers at registered or licensed FBO are mandated to be FSS certified at any point of time. In 2017, Food Safety Supervisor trainings started with the first pool of certified ToT trainers & assessors.

Literature Review: A study conducted in United States of America concluded that “Globalization has triggered growing consumer demand for a wider variety of foods, resulting in an increasingly complex and longer global food chain. Unsafe food creates a vicious cycle of disease and malnutrition affecting infants, young children, elderly and the sick. Because food supply chains cross multiple national and regional borders, collaboration between governments, producers, suppliers, distributors and consumers will ultimately ensure food safety in the 21st century”(Fung, Wang, & Menon, 2018). Another case study done on food handlers at hospitals in Lebanon, where “It was highlighted that the overall food safety knowledge score was low, suggesting thus the need for continuous trainings for food handlers that could improve it, generate positive attitudes and improve safe food handling practices which could contribute to enforce food safety in hospitals” (Bou-Mitri, Mahmoud, El Gerjes, & Jaoude, 2018).

In specific study done on food handlers at a tertiary care hospital in India, it came to the notice that “With the advent of the FSSA 2006 in India, it is mandatory for all food handlers to undergo compulsory medical examination and training and the responsibility of which rests with the FBO or authorities in case of a Hospital. The intervention

package (training; booklet, short films, lectures, posters display) was useful in improving the knowledge, creating a positive attitude and enhancing the food safety practices of food handlers working inside a tertiary care hospital. Meaningful and focused trainings can contribute to improve both the safety and quality of food” (Dudeja, Singh, Sahni, Kaur, & Goel, 2017). Study on food service staff at Universities in Jordan revealed that “Respondents from external managed establishments or enrolled in food safety training were more likely to have more food safety knowledge than those from internal managed establishments or did not enrol in food safety training. This research revealed the importance of education and consistent training of food foodservice staff coupled with effective implementation of HACCP system in reducing the risk of food poisoning in foodservice establishments at the universities in Jordan” (Osaili, Al-Nabulsi, & Allah Krasneh, 2018).

A large study was done on low and middle income countries and it was found that “Every year, hundreds of thousands of deaths result from foodborne disease globally. Although the burden disproportionately falls on consumers in low- and middle-income countries, food safety tends to receive less attention from consumers and policy makers in these countries” (Hoffmann, Moser, & Saak, 2019). In a review study done on food handlers from 06 developed countries highlighted the need of “Food safety managers in food service establishments may consider re-evaluating their current food safety training program to incorporate behavioural-based food safety training in addition to knowledge-based training. In addition to behaviour-based training, continuous and refresher training is critical in maintaining good food handler knowledge and behaviour. Because of the significant increase in knowledge, refresher training would be highly valuable. Though no significant changes in behaviour were observed, the positive correlation found between food safety behaviour and knowledge showed that behaviour is highly related to acquiring knowledge” (McFarland, Checinska Sielaff, Rasco, & Smith, 2019). A review study on food safety training topics for 08 group of food handlers from different countries showed “While most studies reported knowledge increase post intervention, few reported behaviour change. A lack of novel approaches to conveying food safety content was noted” (Reynolds &

Dolasinski, 2019).

In a meta-analysis study of food safety training data from literature of 22 years it is found that “Effective and frequent food safety training of food handlers continues to be an initial step in ensuring that food safety concepts are at least introduced. Despite knowledge being delivered by training, it cannot just be translated into desired changes in attitudes and practice. The inclusion of practical demonstration and continuous support might increase positive attitudes towards food safety and hygiene practices among food handlers with the ultimate goal of minimizing the incidence and prevalence of foodborne hazards. Moreover, effective food safety training should be relevant to the situation, promote active learning, increase risk perception, and consider the work environment. Because computer-based (CB) training was not found to differ from face-to-face training in terms of the outcome obtained, CB programs could be used more extensively, since they are an efficient and cost-effective way to educate staff” (Insfran-Rivarola et al., 2020).

A study conducted on developing countries food safety training evaluated that “there is no translation of knowledge into attitudes/practices or attitudes into practices after training. Some satisfactory results were observed in this triad when more advanced techniques of education and training were used. Knowledge, attitudes and practices of food handlers are important for identifying how efficient training in food safety is allowing prioritize actions in planning the training” (Zanin, da Cunha, de Rosso, Capriles, & Stedefeldt, 2017). Through a food industry multi-sector study the result concluded that “the instructional design literature and results of the food safety training interventions evaluated in this review, it appears that a systematic approach to training design, starting with a front-end analysis and ending with evaluation, may be most appropriate to design training that has a positive impact on behaviours. The instructional design process is systematic and each step plays an important role in developing training that will have the greatest impact on learning outcomes” (Cotter, Yamamoto, & Stevenson, 2023).

Objective of the Study: In India, food industry is divided into 02 broad categories – Organized and Unorganized. Organized is the category which is either registered or licensed with the FSSAI. Unorganized food sector is prominently the micro or small entrepreneurs who

are self-employed and not registered or licensed with the FSSAI. As per latest FSSAI annual report published, we have more than 1.1 crore registered and licensed FBO’s in India. If we consider 02 people employed by each FBO, the total number of food handlers would be more than 2.2 crore. FoSTaC has trained around 20 lakh FSS out of 2.2 crore food handlers across India in 8 years which is 09.09 %.

To train each FH, it will take more than 50 years to cover all FHs. As per latest policy, FSS certificate validity is for 02 years and refresher training needs to be done every 02 years. With this requirement, first time and refresher training equals to a large number of FSS trainings which increases with time, as number of registrations and licenses are increasing every year. Authors are not able to find any research study on FoSTaC certification which is the only regulated and recorded food safety training for FBO’s in India. We want to fulfil this research gap through this study to find out the impact and low reach of the training.

Methodology: FoSTaC training is mandatory for organized sector of food industry in India. Population for the study are food handlers working with registered or licensed FBOs in India. FoSTaC training is mandatory but need to be asked by FBO for food handlers working with him. Therefore, we have done this study through non-parametric convenience sampling method, which is FHs who are participating in the FoSTaC training. Data was collected pre and post training from FHs present at 23 advanced catering FSS trainings.

For quantitative analysis, a structured questionnaire was prepared and tested with 88 respondents for the validity and reliability of the data. As per krejcie and morgan table for finite population of above 100000 population, we are required to get 384 responses for this data collection. A total of 479 responses were recorded and 459 were found to be reliable and without any bias for data analysis (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

Result & Findings:

Hypothesis 1 Testing:

H_0 – The mean score of food safety knowledge of food handlers before training = 70

H_1 – The mean score of food safety knowledge of food handlers before training is not = 70

Descriptive Statistics for Gap (Before-70)

N	459
Mean	-34.7631
Median	-35
Mode	-45 > Mean, Median
Std Deviation	12.01812
Variance	144.4351
Skewness	0.152068
Kurtosis	-0.43914

Test for Normality (Observation)

Test	Statistic	p Value
Shapiro-Wilk	W 0.967459	Pr > W >0.0001
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	D 0.12507	Pr > D >0.0100

Interpretation: p-value is less than 0.05, therefore reject null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis. Indicating that data do not follow normal distribution hence we used non-parametric test which is Wilcoxon Signed rank test.

Tests for Location: Mu0=0

Test	Statistic	p Value
Sign	M -171	Pr >= M >.0001
Signed Rank	S -29326.5	Pr >= S >.0001

Interpretation: p-value is less than 0.05, therefore reject null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis.

Conclusion: Gap is identified & significant (95% confidence with alpha value 0.05) in food safety knowledge of food handlers before the training.

Hypothesis 2 Testing:

H₀ – Training has no impact on food safety knowledge level of Food Handlers. [Difference in Score <= 0 i.e. After Score – Before Score <= 0]

H₁ – Training has impact on food safety knowledge level of Food Handlers. [Difference in Score > 0 i.e. After Score – Before Score > 0]

Descriptive Statistics for Diff. (After Score – Before Score)

N	459
Mean	42.255
Median	41.25
Mode	60 > Mean , Median
Std Deviation	15.012
Variance	225.374
Skewness	-0.291
Kurtosis	-0.1052

Test for Normality

Test	Statistic	p Value
Shapiro-Wilk	W 0.986522	Pr > W >0.0028
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	D 0.070016	Pr > D >0.0100

Interpretation: p-value is less than 0.05, therefore reject null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis.

Conclusion: Alternate hypothesis is “Difference in score not following normal distribution”. We need to do non-parametric test “Wilcoxon Signed-rank test”.

Tests for Location: Mu0=0

Test	Statistic	p Value
Sign	M 170.5	Pr >= M >.0001
Signed Rank	S 29155.5	Pr >= S >.0001

Interpretation: p-value is less than 0.05, therefore reject null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis.

Conclusion: Difference in score is positive and significant, which means training had positive impact in food safety knowledge of Food Handlers.

For qualitative research, expert interview of 18 FoSTaC trainer, assessor and empanelled training partner were conducted. These were organized online and recorded with systematically designed questionnaire. Findings of the quantitative research analysis were compared with expert’s interview. Based on the comparison, 02 Focus Group Discussion (FGD) of 06-08 experts was conducted in January & February 2024. Objective of the discussions was to find the solutions for the challenges in FSS certifications.

Common findings from qualitative research confirmed with quantitative data analysis are as follows:

1. FSS trainings are significant in filling the gap of food safety knowledge in FHs.
2. It is covering all aspects of food safety hazard, how to identify them through various senses, processes & technical tools with guidelines to follow for eliminating them from the system.
3. Variety of training methods like lecture, presentation, video and discussion are followed.
4. Need is to have content prepared and delivered in local language for better understanding by FHs.
5. This training is considered important as legal requirement by FBOs in comparison to food safety knowledge upgrading for FHs.

6. Feedback from FHs and food safety experts are to make basic training mandatory for all FHs to enhance the reach.

7. Refresher training is a significant need of FHs and concurred by experts.

8. Experts would like to have up gradation of FSS training manual regularly.

9. Policy change is advised for including basic food safety training in school education for increasing consumer awareness and developing food safety behaviour in the society.

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ACRONYMS

FSSAI – Food Safety & Standards Authority of India
 FSSA, 2006 – Food Safety & Standards Act, 2006
 FoSTaC – Food Safety Training & Certification
 FSS – Food Safety Supervisor
 ETP – Empanelled Training Partner
 ToT – Training of Trainers
 HACCP – Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point
 CB – Computer Based
 FGD – Focus Group Discussion